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Analysis of Mangrove Health in Batu Karas, Pangandaran, Using NDVI Method Based on Sentinel-2 Satellite Imagery

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to assess the health of the mangroves in Batu Karas using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) method and images from the Sentinel-2 satellite. The data used comes from 2020, 2021, and 2023 to evaluate changes in mangrove conditions. The analysis process includes downloading satellite imagery, cropping it to focus on the mangrove area, supervised classification, and NDVI calculation. The results of the study showed that the area and health of the mangrove ecosystem in Batu Karas experienced a significant increase. The area of mangroves increased from 17 hectares in 2020 to 22 hectares in 2023, while the mangrove health index in the very good category increased from 1.93% in 2020 to 72.18% in 2023. This increase was attributed to the reduction of anthropogenic activities due to the abandonment of ecotourism, as well as the environmental conditions that support the growth of mangroves. This study shows that monitoring mangrove ecosystems using the NDVI method can provide accurate and efficient results in assessing mangrove health. The results of this study are expected to be a reference for Batu Karas ecotourism managers in maintaining and optimizing mangrove ecosystem conservation in the area.

Keywords: Mangrove, NDVI, Batu Karas, Sentinel-2, Ecotourism

Introduction

Indonesia has a long coastline of 95,572.93 km², of which only about 36.07% is covered by mangroves (Global Mangrove Watch, 2016). Several mangrove forest areas are managed by local communities so that they can provide benefits for the community and for the lives of animals around them (Nurdiana, 2020; Suprpto et al., 2015). One of the mangrove areas managed by the community is the Batu Karas area, Pangandaran, to become a Mangrove Ecotourism (Putri et al., 2020). In addition to the Mangrove Ecotourism Area, Batu Karas is a *fishing base* for fishermen and a place for shrimp ponds. (Putra et al., 2018). The management of the mangrove ecosystem in Batu Karas, although managed by the surrounding community, has in fact received less attention so that it is

not managed properly (Amiruddin, 2020). So there is a potential for degradation that can occur in the Batu Karas mangrove ecosystem because it is not managed properly by the manager, and many pollutants come from shrimp ponds around Batu Karas (Pranata, 2018).

No one knows for sure the condition of the mangrove health in Batu Karas because there is no control over the health of the mangroves in Batu Karas. (Amiruddin, 2020). Controlling the health of mangroves has been done by other researchers before. This method, which uses satellite images and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) method, is thought to work well for controlling mangrove health (Kawamuna et al., 2017). The NDVI algorithm can calculate the light reflected from mangrove leaves so that it can produce its health index (Syamsu et al., 2018). Through health control carried out using this method, it will shorten the time for analyzing the health of the mangroves to be studied, but to ensure its accuracy, field validation is still needed (Akbar et al., 2020). This research is important to be conducted to provide input for the management of Mangrove Ecotourism in Batu Karas, Pangandaran regarding the control of the quality of mangrove health in Batu Karas, Pangandaran. This research serves as a reference for future arguments regarding the health or damage of the mangrove ecosystem in Batu Karas, Pangandaran.

Method

The study took place in Batu Karas, Pangandaran, in April 2024. Sentinel-2 image data from 2020 and 2023 were used to see what changes happened, as well as field data from 2023. The coordinates of the data station were 7.7200618 LS, 108.4971497 BT (Figure 1). This point was taken based on the position of the mangrove ecosystem in Batu Karas; the estimated area of this point is around 9.34 hectares (Globalforestwatch.org, 2016).

Figure 1. The Area of Interest

Sentinel Data Collection 2

Currently, you can download Sentinel 2 data using Google Chrome at <https://scihub.copernicus.eu>. The downloaded data is for June 2020 and June 2023, according to the years needed. We chose these 2 years to compare the conditions before and after the area's abandonment. The downloaded image is also level 2 so that the data has been atmospherically corrected.

Image Cropping

After the data is obtained and can be displayed in the SNAP application, the visible data will be centered on the data to be processed, which can be called *the Area of Interest*. The purpose of determining this *area of interest* is so that later the data to be processed is not too heavy and effective to be able to process mangrove data in Batukaras. *The area near the mangrove and the mangrove forest to be analyzed will be the data study area.*

Supervised Classification

The next step after subsetting the data is to classify the image data using supervised classification. The SNAP software validates this classification by creating a training area. We selected the sea, mangrove, pond, and sand as the training area due to their distinct positions and colors.

NDVI Algorithm

After supervision, the NDVI algorithm receives the image data using the following formula:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{Band 8} - \text{Band 4}}{\text{Band 8} + \text{Band 4}}$$

Information:

Band 4 = Red Band

Band 8 = Near Infrared (NIR) Band

NDVI will produce an index from -0.1 to 1 indicating the health of mangroves in the studied area. The green reflection of mangrove leaves yields this number, which the existing image data will subsequently mirror.

Results and discussion

The NDVI classification data tells us about the health of mangroves. NDVI will collect health data in Batu Karas in 2020 and 2023 by measuring the amount of light that plants reflect.

Mangrove Health Index Analysis

Based on the processed results, it was found that the area increased significantly by 5 hectares, and also an increase in the quality of mangrove health, which increased when the index was very good in 2020 by 1.93%, increasing sharply in 2023. The index was very good at 72.18%. The index was very good with these results, increasing by 70.25%. These results indicate an improvement in the condition of the mangroves in Batu Karas from 2020 to 2023 (Figure 2). This mangrove condition can be caused by several influencing factors: anthropogenic factors, natural conditions, and the growth patterns of the mangroves themselves. Anthropogenic factors are one of the factors that affect the condition of the mangrove ecosystem (Sunarto, 2008). Anthropogenic factors that occur in the Batu Karas mangrove are that there are not many activities occurring around the area due to the neglect of ecotourism in Batu Karas, marked by damage to facilities that support the Batu Karas mangrove ecotourism. This causes activities that occur around the Batu Karas mangrove to decrease because there are no tourists visiting Batu Karas.

Figure 2. Mangrove raster health condition in AoI

One of the abandoned or damaged facilities in the Batu Karas mangrove ecotourism is the ecotourism bridge that supports tourists to be able to do activities around the Batu Karas mangrove. After ecotourism was abandoned in Batu Karas, the ecotourism bridge in Figure 16 was damaged. This bridge is the only way to enjoy mangrove ecotourism in Batu Karas (Amiruddin, 2020). With this condition, tourists cannot visit the ecotourism area in Batu Karas. So there are no tourist activities around the Batu Karas ecotourism area. Apart from the damaged bridge and abandoned ecotourism, another anthropogenic factor around the Batu Karas mangrove is the large number of shrimp ponds around the area. These ponds affect the activities of the surrounding community, thus affecting the condition of the mangroves in Batu Karas (Pranata, 2018). The ponds produce waste, but it doesn't significantly hinder the growth of the mangroves in Batu Karas. The number of ponds is still within reasonable limits in the Batu Karas area so that the Batu Karas mangrove area can still grow and reproduce in the area optimally (Adiprima & Sudrajat, 2008).

Natural factors also influence the growth and health of mangroves. One of the natural factors influencing the growth of mangroves is the physical parameters of the water surrounding the Batu Karas mangrove. The water quality parameters in the Batu Karas mangrove support mangrove growth with an average water quality that is suitable for mangrove growth. Nurdiana (2020) indicates that the Batu Karas mangrove area exhibits maximum phytoplankton growth activity. Apart from the macrozoobenthos phytoplankton found in Batu Karas, it is very diverse and supports growth in the ecosystem (Nurfajrin, 2018).

Conclusion

Mangrove health in Batu Karas from 2020 to 2023 has increased or improved from year to year. This is indicated by the increasing area and health index at the very good index, which has increased from year to year. The area of mangrove in 2020 was 17 hectares, and in 2023 it was 19 hectares. The increase that occurred was the area of mangrove increased by 2 hectares from 2020 to 2023, and the very good index in 2020 was 1.93%; in 2020 it was 13.72%, and in 2023 it was 72.18%, so the increase that occurred in the mangrove health index from year to year was 70.25%.

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